

CAUSES, TYPES, SYMPTOMS AND TREATMENT METHODS OF PROSTATITIS DISEASES THAT OCCUR IN THE HUMAN BODY TODAY.

Kilichev Jasurbek Fayzullayevich¹

¹Faculty of Medicine, Termiz Branch, Tashkent
Medical Academy Student

To'raqulova Marjona Zulfiqor qizi²

²Faculty of Medicine, Termiz Branch, Tashkent
Medical Academy Student

Tursunaliyeva Vahoba Umarali qizi³

³Faculty of Medicine, Termiz Branch, Tashkent
Medical Academy Student

Menglibayeva Nozima Ikrom qizi⁴

⁴Faculty of Medicine, Termiz Branch, Tashkent
Medical Academy Student

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Abstract: Today, various prostatic processes occurring in the human body have a very negative effect on the human body. What kind of disease is prostatitis? Whether it's a headache, frustration, or stomach ache. How can we prevent this disease? How much money and how much time will it take to prevent the disease can be found in this article.

Key words: Prostatitis, Prostatitis causes, Prostate function, Prostatitis onset, Types, Chronic prostatitis, Prevention

Purpose: Prevention and treatment of prostatitis

Introduction: Prostatitis is an inflammation of the prostate gland. The prostate gland is a secondary part of the male reproductive organs. The gland is located under the bladder, around its neck. The urinary channel (urethra) passes through the prostate, that is, the prostate surrounds the urethra. For this reason, when the prostate enlarges, it compresses the urethra and prevents the passage of urine.

Prostate enlargement is often observed in men over 35 years of age. This is a common occurrence. In men over 50 years of age, the disease is a consequence of the dysfunction of the urinary-genital system, that is, as a result of inflammation of the prostate gland. It should be remembered that the larger the prostate gland, the more urine is blocked, and thus the body becomes more and more poisoned with urine. The disease is quite common and is diagnosed in more than 80% of sexually mature men, about 30% of which are found in the age group of 20 to 40 years. If we refer to statistical studies, prostatitis is detected in every 10 patients.

Causes of prostatitis: The main cause of prostatitis is blood circulation disorder, which leads to enlargement of the prostate gland. The cause of blood circulation disorders is a sedentary and inactive lifestyle, as well as high weight. Another cause of prostatitis is infection. Most often, infection occurs as a result of gonorrhea or urethritis, less often - as a result of complications of angina, influenza, tuberculosis. Bacterial inflammation of the prostate begins when bacterial agents enter the prostate gland through blood, lymph, unprotected sex, in other words, after passing through the body's biological fluids. Various microorganisms that are constantly present on the human skin can even cause the development of diseases in the organs of the abdominal cavity, for example, in the intestine, under certain conditions. Injuries of small pelvic organs and soft tissues, their blood

circulation disorders often lead to prostatitis. As a rule, this applies to drivers who are often associated with occupational hazards - constant vibration, shaking, excessive muscle strain. Also, frequent colds and low physical activity, chronic urogenital diseases or hormonal imbalance, urinary retention and irregular sexual life also contribute to the development of the disease. Inflammation in the rectum or urethra often causes secondary infection of the prostate gland. Causes of prostatitis include urological infections and some venereal diseases, such as gonorrhea or urethritis. Chronic diseases such as bronchitis, tonsillitis, and untreated dental caries can also cause this disease. The immune system also plays a role in the development of this disease. Because as a result of bad habits, emotional worries, malnutrition, physical fatigue, immunity weakens, and the human body has difficulty fighting against various infectious agents, including those that cause inflammation of the prostate gland.

Functions of the prostate gland:

1. It produces a fluid that is part of sperm
2. Testosterone is converted into its active form, dihydrotestosterone
3. Together with the muscles of the bladder neck, it forms an internal sphincter that controls the process of urination.
4. Participates in the management of the body's emotions

Symptoms of prostatitis (onset): Symptoms of acute prostatitis are fever and frequent urination, with painful urination and weak pressure. In addition, symptoms of prostatitis may include pain in the rectum and discomfort during defecation. In the stage of purulent inflammation, it is unlikely that the abscess will rupture on its own and discharge pus from the urine or rectum.

Symptoms of chronic prostatitis include pain in the urethra and interstitium, discharge of pus at the end of defecation or urination, rapid fatigue and affectation of the body. Difficulty urinating in prostatitis is very dangerous, if it is not treated in time, it can lead to acute retention of urine. Men should not ignore indirect signs of prostatitis development, such as complete or partial loss of sexual interest, rapid ejaculation, sometimes painful, long-lasting erections at night. All these symptoms are typical for inflammation of the prostate gland at a stage that is not yet complicated and can be treated relatively easily. If we talk about the manifestations that are known even to non-specialists, in most cases, patients note the discharge of transparent and sometimes purulent discharge from the urethra in the morning, and the detection of white dots and fibers in the urine.

Types of prostatitis: Bacterial prostatitis - Microorganisms that cause disease of the prostate gland: *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus*, *Klebsella*, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Most of these bacteria are the normal microflora of the human body, they live in the intestines and skin. When these bacteria enter the prostate gland, they cause inflammation and can have a very negative effect on the human body. Often, these bacteria can enter the prostate gland through the bladder and urethra, and from the intestines through blood vessels.

Chronic form. In contrast to the acute form, chronic prostatitis is asymptomatic and latent (that is, without noticeable symptoms). The clinical picture is often vague, patients do not pay enough attention to serious discomfort and consider it unnecessary to consult a doctor, they confuse the symptoms of prostatitis with adenoma of the prostate gland. The

principles of treatment of these two diseases are completely different, as well as complications and consequences. Often, feelings of malaise, problems with sexual energy and nervousness of a man spread to fatigue and restlessness, which means that a person does not recognize that he is sick and needs medical help. Annual preventive examinations, which are important for the timely detection of this disease, allow to diagnose the disease in the early stages. The chronic form of the inflammatory process is manifested by pains that are not noticeable and quickly disappear in the region of the intercostal space. Usually, the duration of sexual intercourse changes, it can be prolonged or, on the contrary, reduced, the brightness of sexual feelings also changes. Discharges from the urinary tract are observed, especially in the mornings, or there are white substances in the urine. Urinary disorders occur due to the inflammatory process leading to compression of the urethral cavity, and men should pay attention to this in the first place: the flow of urine is weak, there is a drop, and the head of the urethra or difficulties may arise in the end. Many patients note that they have observed incomplete emptying of the bladder or uncontrollable flow of urine. The inflammatory process has an excitatory effect on the nerve endings, and as a result, there are frequent urges to urinate, especially in the evening, when urination is small. These symptoms indicate the development of a pathological process and require immediate medical attention. Only a specialist can make a correct diagnosis and prescribe the necessary treatment. Unfortunately, behind these symptoms, a terrible disease such as prostate cancer may be hidden. If the inflammatory process of the prostate gland begins to heal in time, it does not cause significant disturbances in the sexual sphere. However, in the absence of treatment, loss of sexual desire and infertility often develop in men of reproductive age. The most common complications of untreated prostatitis are secondary urinary tract infections and the development of kidney failure. Bladder stones and urinary retention are no less dangerous. The disease develops and covers the urinary bladder - due to the deterioration of blood circulation, the excretion of urine is disturbed and its walls become sclerosed, these pathological changes are irreversible. Prevention of prostatitis If the patient does not consult a doctor in time, suppuration may appear in the prostate gland later. In such cases, the body temperature rises to 39-40 degrees, severe pain is felt in the urinary tract.

It should not be forgotten that the chronic form of the disease is dangerous with a complicated course. This disease is hidden in the human body for many years, so it does not make itself felt. That is why many men do not know that they have a prostate gland. Over time, the situation becomes more complicated due to inflammation of the gland. This process in a man's body can later pass to the urinary tract and cause the following diseases:

- ② cystitis (bladder inflammation);
- ② pyelonephritis (kidney and kidney cyst
- ② blood from top to bottom of the mucous membrane
- ② descending through or ascending from below the urinary tract
- ② inflammation through infection);
- ② vesiculitis (inflammation of seminal vesicles);
- ② epididymorchitis (inflammation of the testicles and their appendages).

TREATMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC PROSTATITIS

Although prostatitis has been known for a long time and is common among men of all ages, it can be difficult to treat. will not be possible. Scientists have many opinions about how to treat chronic inflammation of the prostate gland.

However, there is no disagreement among experts on the following paragraphs:

- ☒ Effectiveness of treatment directly depends on timely initiation;
- ☒ Treatment should be carried out comprehensively, taking into account all the specific health conditions of an individual patient. It is very important to determine the cause that led to the development of pathology;
- ☒ There are no single drugs and treatment methods. What helped the first patient may harm the second;
- ☒ Independent diagnosis and treatment is strictly prohibited.

Modern methods of treatment of prostatitis

Currently, patients suffering from prostatitis are cured with the help of painless and effective treatment methods. To do this, they must first undergo the following checks:

- computer scanning;
- three-way ultrasound diagnosis;
- Immunoenzymatic treatment – PSA (prostate specific antigen).
- After studying the final results of the patient, he was diagnosed with prostatitis, adenoma, i.e. hyperplasia (tumor arising from glandular tissue) or prostate gland it can be clearly diagnosed as cancer.

Conclusion: Patients diagnosed with this disease do not need to be depressed. Because scientists have already developed a way to cure the pain of such patients. Treatment of prostate cancer in the initial period gives a positive result. But if a secondary tumor (metastasis) formed as a result of the spread of malignant tumor cells from the primary site to other organs with the flow of blood or lymph, the treatment of the disease becomes difficult. . That's why I advise men to have a doctor's check-up from time to time.

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